

Learning from demonstrations without parameter tuning for an industrial cobot

Lorenzo Panchetti, Jianhao Zheng
*ReGIS EPFL
 Schindler*
 Lausanne, Switzerland
 firstname.surname@schindler.com

Mohamed Bouri
*Biorobotics Laboratory
 EPFL*
 Lausanne, Switzerland
 mohamed.bouri@epfl.com

Nicola Ischia
*ReGIS Milan
 Schindler*
 Milan, Italy
 nicola.ischia@schindler.com

Malcolm Mielle
*ReGIS EPFL
 Schindler*
 Lausanne, Switzerland
 malcolm.mielle@schindler.com

Abstract—State-of-the-art learning from demonstration (LfD) methods for collaborative robots—skill transfer and generalization through a set of demonstrations—require manually tuning intrinsic parameters. Hence, LfD cannot be used readily in industrial contexts without experts.

We propose a parameter-free method based on probabilistic movement primitives, where all the parameters are pre-determined using Jensen-Shannon divergence and Bayesian Optimization method, so users do not perform any tuning. This method learns motions from a small dataset of user demonstrations, and generalizes the motion to various scenarios and conditions with no manual tuning.

We evaluate our method in field tests where the cobot works with Schindler workers in the field. We show errors between the cobot end-effector and target positions ranging from 0 to 1.479 ± 0.351 mm, and no task failures for all tests. Questionnaires completed by Schindler workers highlighted our method’s ease of use, feeling of safety, and the accuracy of the reproduced motion.

I. INTRODUCTION

Learning from demonstration (LfD) [1]—a branch of learning focused on skill transfer and generalization through a set of demonstrations—enables cobots to learn and adapt motions. However, state-of-the-art LfD methods require manually tuning intrinsic parameters [2]–[4] and have thus rarely been used in industrial contexts without experts roboticists. We propose a method to learn from demonstrations without parameters tuning, and the main contributions are:

- Development of a parameter-free framework to learn motions from a set of demonstrations based on generative models to generalize trajectories and attractor landscapes to reproduce the motion between different start and end joint angles.
- An optimization strategy of attractor landscape’s parameters based on Bayesian optimization and an improvement of the selection of the number of generative models’ Gaussians through Jensen-Shannon divergence.
- Implementation and experimental validation of a field test showing that our method can be used by naive users.

The general process employed is shown in Fig. 1.

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Fig. 1. A set of demonstrations is recorded by a user and the motion is generalized through GMR. Then, the system is modelled as a set of damped spring models that can generalize the motion to different start and end positions.

II. METHOD

A demonstration stores the cobot’s joints angles recorded while the robot is manually moved to demonstrate the task. Demonstrations are obtained in joint space to be able to use redundant robot arms, without worrying about singularities during motion. From a set of demonstrations for a given task collected by the user, the first step is to compute a reference trajectory. All demonstrations are aligned in time using dynamic time warping [5] and we use the Jensen-Shannon (JS) divergence [6] to fit a Gaussian mixture model (GMM) on the demonstration dataset. Finally, we calculate the Gaussian Mixture Regression (GMR)—which corresponds to our generalized model trajectory.

Building on previous work on ProMP [7] and attractor landscape [3], we create a damped spring model for each joint:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau \dot{z} &= \alpha_z (\beta_z (g - y) - z) + f \\ \dot{y} &= z \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where τ is a time constant, f is the nonlinear forcing term, and α_z and β_z are positive constants. To reproduce the GMR, the forcing term f of Eq. (1) is learned. Since f is a

Fig. 2. The cobot interaction is evaluated in terms of safety, easiness to teach, entertainment, goal achievement, and task completion. Three answers have been collected for results in the chart on the right, featuring two different users. A user participated in the activities twice, its second feedback is shown in dashed lines.

nonlinear function, it can be represented as a normalized linear combination of N basis functions [8].

With $4\beta_z = \alpha_z$ [3], Bayes optimization is used to estimate the damped spring model parameters α_z and N . Finally, A spring model is estimated for each degree of freedom and a shared canonical system [3] synchronize them in time.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

Public implementation¹ can be found online. We use the 6 axis ABB GoFa CRB 15000 cobot.² Pose repeatability at the maximum reach and load is 0.05 mm, and axis resolution is $1.74 \cdot 10^{-5}$ rad. We conducted field tests at the Schindler headquarters in Ebikon. To be realistic, the scenarios were designed with field workers:

- $F1$: find a metal piece and place it on a drilling machine.
- $F2$: find a metal piece and place it on a drilling machine while avoiding the worker on the machine.
- $F3$: find a metal frame and place it on a drilling machine while rotating the piece.
- $F4$: find a wooden plank, grab one side while the worker grabs the other, and, place it together on a drilling machine.

Object detection is done with template matching on depth image from a 3D depth camera.

The tests were conducted by three Schindler workers, and for each task, three and five demonstrations per user were collected. Statistics presented in Table I were calculated on 30 reproductions of the motion for each task.

A. User survey

At the end of each day, workers answered a questionnaire to evaluate the cobot’s performance. In the survey, users rate the following statements on a scale from 1 to 5, corresponding to strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree:

- The cobot learned the correct motion.
- I felt safe operating the cobot.
- The cobot reached the goal point accurately.
- Teaching the cobot a motion was simple.

¹<https://github.com/SchindlerReGIS/team>

²<https://new.abb.com/products/robotics/collaborative-robots/crb-15000>

TABLE I

THIS TABLE PRESENTS ERROR METRICS FOR FACTORY TASKS—30 RUNS ARE PERFORMED PER TASK. FAILURES CORRESPOND TO THE NUMBER OF TIME THE ROBOT EITHER BY NOT REPRODUCING THE MOVEMENT OR FAILED AT COMPLETING THE TASK—THIS WAS EVALUATED VISUALLY.

Task	F1	F2	F3	F4
Name	Drill	Avoid	Parallel	Collaborative
Position error e_p [mm]	0 ± 0	0.153 ± 0.026	0.536 ± 0.646	0.295 ± 0.291
Orientation error e_θ	$5.2 \cdot 10^{-5} \pm 3.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$9.6 \cdot 10^{-4} \pm 7.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.7 \cdot 10^{-4} \pm 5.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.001 ± 0.001
Joints error e_j [rad]	0.618 ± 0.517	0.580 ± 0.274	0.573 ± 0.228	0.594 ± 0.199
Failures	0	0	0	0

- Teaching the cobot a motion was entertaining.

The radar plots in Fig. 2 present the survey’s results. While users show satisfaction with the cobot’s precision and motion performance, the complexity of holding the beam and moving the cobot while demonstrating the motion in F4 lead to lower score for easiness of teaching compared to other tasks.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a novel parameter-free method for learning from demonstrations was presented. The method can be used by naive users since it does not need manual tuning. Field tests in real-world scenario were conducted to validate the method. The cobot never failed to perform a motion and questionnaires completed by Schindler workers highlighted the method’s ease of use, feeling of safety, and the accuracy of the reproduced motion.

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